

1 **Tracing quartz provenance:**
2 **a multi-method investigation of luminescence sensitisation mechanisms of quartz**
3 **from granite source rocks and derived sediments**
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25 **Abstract**

26 Quartz optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) sensitivity as well as some electron spin
27 resonance (ESR) and cathodoluminescence (CL) signals have been empirically proposed as
28 provenance indicators. Sensitivity is defined as luminescence emitted in response to a given dose
29 per unit mass. While it is largely believed to be acquired by earth surface processes, recent studies
30 bring evidence that sensitisation processes depend on source geology.

31 Here we combine OSL and thermoluminescence (TL), ESR and CL analyses to understand the
32 mechanisms of quartz OSL sensitisation. We investigate granites and their derived sediments from
33 catchments draining simple lithologies of known age that display contrasting OSL sensitisation
34 behaviour both in nature and during irradiation and light exposure laboratory experiments. The
35 sample displaying increased OSL sensitisation is characterised by TL emission at intermediate
36 temperatures (150-250 °C), Ti-related signals in CL, and Ti and Ge lithium compensated signals
37 in ESR. The insensitive samples either lack or exhibit very weak such characteristics and contain
38 several times less amount of trace titanium measured by laser ablation inductively coupled plasma
39 mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS).

40 We demonstrate that the OSL sensitisation by irradiation and light exposure, results as an effect of
41 the existence of certain defects and impurities in the quartz crystal in the parent rock, such as
42 titanium and germanium. However, the degree of sensitisation reached in nature is significantly

43 higher than in the laboratory. As such, the existence of this precursor represents the potential for
44 sensitisation by irradiation and illumination. Sensitivity can later be amplified by other
45 environmental factors that remain to be identified.

46 ***Key words:** provenance; quartz; granites; sediments; multi-spectral analysis; elemental analysis.*

47 **1. Introduction**

48 Provenance studies offer valuable insights into the origins and history of sediments, particularly
49 concerning tectonic processes and paleoclimate dynamics. Through analytical techniques,
50 sediment sources influenced by tectonic events such as orogeny and erosion can be identified (**e.g.,**
51 **Dickinson and Suczek, 1979; Garzanti, 2016; Basu et al., 2016**), as well as paleoclimatic
52 conditions (**e.g., Clift et al., 2008**). In sedimentary basin research, provenance analysis is essential
53 for reconstructing sediment routing systems, typically tracing from sink to source. While these
54 analyses rely on mineral composition, the physical alterations minerals undergo during transport
55 and storage largely remain open questions (**Caracciolo, 2020**).

56 Durability and abundance of quartz ensures that the parent rocks containing quartz are represented
57 by detrital quartz in their daughter sediment (**Basu, 1985**). However, most provenance studies are
58 based on accessory minerals, the most popular being zircon, apatite and titanite, since all can be
59 dated by U-Th-Pb geochronology. The abundance of these minerals may not correlate with
60 sediment mass and can bias results toward petrologic processes that produce them in large
61 quantities.

62 Quartz contains a substantial number of point defects, even in high-purity samples. These defects
63 can be intrinsic, such as oxygen and silicon vacancies, or extrinsic, typically resulting from
64 impurities involving monovalent (H^+ , Li^+ , Na^+) and trivalent (Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , B^{3+}) cations (**Götze, 2009;**

65 **Preusser et al., 2009**). Some defects remain stable under ionising radiation from natural sources,
66 particularly potassium, uranium, thorium, and cosmic radiation, while others are modified through
67 charge trapping. Paramagnetic defects, such as E' (an unpaired electron at an oxygen vacancy site,
68 $\equiv\text{Si}\cdot$), intrinsic peroxy defect centres ($\equiv\text{Si-O-O}\cdot$), nonbridging oxygen ($\equiv\text{Si-O}\cdot$), aluminium,
69 titanium or germanium-related defects (e.g. $[\text{AlO}_4]^\ominus$, $[\text{TiO}_4\text{-Li}^\oplus]^\ominus$, $[\text{GeO}_4\text{-Li}^\oplus]^\ominus$), can be detected via
70 electron spin resonance (**Weil, 2000; Mashkovtsev and Pan, 2013**). Additionally, certain defects
71 such as nonbridging oxygen (NBOHC, $\equiv\text{Si-O}\cdot$), oxygen deficiency centres (ODC, $\equiv\text{Si-Si}\equiv$), etc.,
72 emit light when stimulated and are characterised by photoluminescence or cathodoluminescence
73 techniques (**Skuja et al., 2020; Stevens-Kalceff, 2009**).

74 The behaviour of the radiation-sensitive defects in quartz under irradiation allows quartz to record
75 the total ionising radiation dose it has received since its last resetting event, storing this information
76 as a latent signal within its crystal lattice. These signals can be stimulated and measured through
77 controlled heating or light exposure (typically using blue light emitting diodes in standard quartz-
78 based procedures) or by exposing the sample to magnetic and microwave fields. As a result, quartz
79 is extensively employed in sediment dating through thermoluminescence (TL), optically
80 stimulated luminescence (OSL) (**Aitken, 1985; 1998**), and electron spin resonance (ESR) (**Ikeya,**
81 **1993**), which are collectively referred to as trapped charge dating methods. The mechanisms
82 underlying the modification due to interactions with natural nuclear radiation are inherently
83 complex. Nevertheless, some relevant studies that explain these phenomena include e.g. **Mackey**
84 **(1963)** and **Halliburton et al. (1981)** on synthetic quartz and **McKeever et al. (1985), Itoh et al.**
85 **(2002), Vaccaro et al. (2017), and Benzid and Timar-Gabor (2020a, b, 2021)** on natural quartz.
86 However, there are still many complex interactions occurring in sedimentary systems that are not

87 completely understood, as defects in the sedimentary quartz grains, or their precursors inherited
88 from the source rock may suffer alterations through weathering and transport.

89 Despite limited understanding of these dynamics, several studies suggest that specific signals and
90 defects are useful for provenance analysis, such as ESR (**Toyoda et al., 2016**) and luminescence
91 (**Gray et al., 2019**). In luminescence studies, the key parameter is OSL sensitivity, which measures
92 the luminescence emitted per unit of radiation dose (in Gray, Gy) for a given sample mass. OSL
93 signals increase with dose, though sensitivity varies by sample (**Preusser et al., 2009**). Although
94 the mechanisms behind OSL production and sensitization remain unclear, empirical studies have
95 increasingly applied quartz OSL sensitivity in provenance research (e.g., **Sawakuchi et al., 2011,**
96 **2018; Jeong and Choi, 2012; Gray et al., 2019; del Río et al., 2021; Mineli et al., 2021**).

97 Initial studies largely concluded that luminescence sensitivity in sediments is acquired by transport
98 processes acting on the grain after being weathered from the original source rock (e.g. **Pietsch et**
99 **al., 2008; Jeong and Choi, 2012; Sawakuchi et al., 2011**). However, later studies did not observe
100 a dependence of the OSL sensitivity with transport distance for sediments derived from Andean
101 terrains in South America (**Sawakuchi et al., 2018**) or from a mountainous catchment in North
102 America (**Tanski et al., 2024**). They report a correlation between OSL sensitivity and denudation
103 rates (**Sawakuchi et al., 2018**) and erosion rates and chemical weathering (**Tanski et al., 2024**).
104 Most recent studies suggest that sensitisation processes are a function of source lithology and
105 crystallisation age (**Capaldi et al., 2022; Alexanderson, 2022; Timar-Gabor et al., 2023; Zhang**
106 **et al., 2023**).

107 A vast majority of the provenance studies target minerals grains deposited in sinks, without
108 examining the signals of the potential sources, not proving a cause-effect relationship. Hence, this
109 study aims to address the gap in knowledge regarding quartz luminescence signals in rocks.

110 Besides the trapped charge methods described above, another method that can provide valuable
111 information on defects in quartz is cathodoluminescence (CL). Quartz of different origins is known
112 to emit in different spectral ranges from red to violet. When combined with ESR spectroscopy and
113 spatially resolved trace-element analysis, it offers insights into the relationship between various
114 luminescence emission bands and specific lattice defects within the quartz structure (Müller 2000;
115 Götze et al. 2001; Stevens-Kalceff 2009; Götze 2009, Leeman et al., 2012). Despite a strong
116 complementarity of CL and OSL/TL methods for understanding the defects in the natural quartz
117 crystals, studies that correlate CL and OSL emissions in natural quartz are currently lacking.

118 Here we apply a multi spectroscopic approach combining OSL, TL, ESR and CL analysis to gain
119 insights into the physical mechanisms of quartz OSL sensitisation. We complement these methods
120 with laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry measurements. We investigate
121 granites and their derived sediments collected from catchment areas draining simple and well-
122 constrained lithologies. The chosen samples display marked sensitisation behaviours both in nature
123 and during laboratory experiments. We demonstrate that the OSL sensitisation in nature is an effect
124 of the existence of certain defects and impurities in the quartz crystal in the parent rock such as
125 titanium and germanium. The existence of this precursor defects represents the potential for
126 sensitisation by light exposure and irradiation cycles, which can be later amplified by other
127 environmental factors during its sedimentary history.

128 **2. Geological background and samples**

129 Here we investigate quartz extracted from two granite rocks and their related sediments from well
130 constrained bedrock lithologies. We chose areas that have a clear and uniform bedrock geology
131 exclusively represented by a uniform granitoid and a sedimentary pathway along rivers that are

132 catching those sources alone. In other words, in each case, the sampling was focused on a simple
133 catchment draining a single granite lithology of known U-Pb zircon crystallisation age.

134 *Catalina granite*

135 The Catalina Intrusive suite (ca. 25 Ma, **Ducea et al., 2020**) is exposed in a roughly semicircular
136 pluton at the north-western edge of the Santa Catalina Mountains, north of the city of Tucson in
137 southeast Arizona, US. The large 10-15 km intrusion in the core of the Catalina detachment system
138 is synchronous with the main latest Oligocene detachment that unroofed the Catalina Mountains
139 as a footwall of a major low angle extensional system. The emplacement of this granitoid is the
140 latest felsic intrusive event regionally, is part of a regional magmatic “flare-up” that coincide with
141 the switch from convergence to continental extension and collapse of a large plateau referred to as
142 the Nevadaplano (**DeCelles, 2004**). The plutonic rocks referred to as “the Catalina granite”
143 comprise a distinctive group of quartz monzonite, tonalites and granodiorites with only minor
144 granite *sensu stricto*. Radiometric age determinations for the Catalina granite include U-Pb zircon
145 crystallisation ages that range from 27 to 25 Ma (**Ducea et al., 2020**) as well as fission track ages
146 on sphene (30-28 Ma), on zircon (29-24 Ma) and on apatite (24 to 21 Ma) (**Creasy et al. 1977**),
147 presumably marking cooling during unroofing. The small difference between the zircon
148 crystallisation ages and the apatite cooling ages indicates a fast exhumation after its formation and
149 crystallisation. For this study, one bedrock sample of Catalina granite was collected (**Figure 1A**).
150 The derived sediment was sampled from the modern wash of one of the tributaries of Oro River,
151 which exclusively drained sediments derived from the Catalina Intrusion. The distance between
152 the bedrock sampling point and sediment sampling is approximately 3.5 km. Details on samples
153 locations are given in **Table S1**.

154 *Retezat mountains, South Carpathians, Romania*

155 Retezat Mountains is one of the distinct ranges of the South Carpathians and is morphologically
156 one of the highest and most glaciated mountains of that area. It consists primarily of the Danubian
157 thrust sheet which exposes basement rocks of pre-Triassic ages. Although in detail the basement
158 (igneous and metamorphic) units making up the Danubian are complex, the central part of the
159 Retezat mountains is much simpler geologically. It comprises multiple plutons together making up
160 an S-type batholith of late Carboniferous to Permian ages. It consists mainly of two mica and
161 garnet bearing leucogranites, although several fabrics and varieties of granites have been mapped,
162 including some less felsic varieties (**Berza et al., 1989**). Early U-Pb zircon ages on Retezat
163 granitoid yielded a 310 ± 5 Ma age (**Balintoni et al., 2014**). Newer age data carried out on multiple
164 plutons indicate the Retezat batholith was formed mostly in the earliest Permian and numerous
165 detrital 290-300 Ma age peaks in modern sediments, that could not have an origin other than
166 Retezat (**Ducea et al., 2018**). Regardless of the detailed ages, the Retezat batholith is part of a
167 regional province of unmetamorphosed granitoids in the Danubian basement. When viewed at
168 larger European scale, these plutons have traditionally been considered (e.g. **Ménard and Molnar,**
169 **1988**) products of magmatism related to the collapse of Variscan orogen. The sedimentary
170 sampling pathway chosen here (along the Pietrele River from the Mountain Crest northward), is
171 restricted to the Retezat granite as a source. An apatite fission track age of 17 ± 2 Ma on chlorite
172 schist was reported by **Bojar et al. (1998)**. This singular age may be insufficient to document
173 Cenozoic uplift but shows that the unroofing of the Danubian took place much more recently than
174 the time of its formation.

175 The sampling followed the modern stream from the range crest along the Pietrele valley (**Figure**
176 **1B**). One bedrock sample was collected from the range crest, one sample from the nearby Pietrele
177 Lake and four samples were taken from the modern stream at about 1 km intervals from headwaters

178 toward the northern foothills covering a distance of about 5 km. The bedrock sample was identified
179 as leucocratic granite. Details about the locations of the Retezat samples are given in **Table S1**.

180 **3. Methods and instrumentation**

181 **3.1. Sample preparation**

182 All analyses were carried out on 250-500 μm quartz extracted from the bedrock and sediment
183 samples following standard procedures detailed in the supplementary material.

184 **3.2. Optically and thermally stimulated luminescence**

185 Luminescence analyses were carried out using TL/OSL Risø DA-20 readers equipped with a
186 $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ beta source with a dose rate of 0.08 Gy/s, an automated detection and stimulation head
187 (DASH) (**Lapp et al., 2015**). The optical stimulation unit consisted of blue LEDs (470 ± 30 nm,
188 80 mW/cm²) and IR LEDs (850 ± 30 nm, 300 mW/cm²). The thermal stimulation was performed
189 through a low-mass Kanthal strip that holds the disk with the sample. The OSL and TL emissions
190 were detected using PDM 9107Q-AP-TTL-03 (160-630 nm) photomultiplier fitted with 7.5 mm
191 Hoya U-340 filters (300-390 nm). The protocol for luminescence measurements is presented in
192 **Table S2** and further details are provided in the supplementary material.

193 **3.3. Electron spin resonance**

194 Electron spin resonance measurements of E'_1 , peroxy, Al-hole ($[\text{AlO}_4]^0$), titanium centres were
195 performed using an X band (9.8 GHz) Bruker EMX Plus Spectrometer. A high sensitivity cavity
196 (ER 4119HS Bruker resonator) with an unloaded quality factor of 15000 and loaded factor of about
197 7800 was used for all investigations. All measurements were made in quartz glass tubes, filled with
198 samples at the same volume. ESR measurements for all the samples were normalised to 100 mg

199 for intercomparison. In all cases, we measure the peak-to-peak amplitude of the ESR signal to
200 quantify the defect concentration as the peak-to-peak amplitude variation can be taken as an
201 approximation for concentration of the defect centres in the sample.

202 Gamma irradiations were performed at the Centre for Nuclear Technologies, Technical University
203 of Denmark, Risø Campus, using a Nordion Gammacell 220 Co-60 gamma irradiator, with a dose
204 rate of 2 Gy/s (dose rate to water) at the time of irradiation. Based on Monte Carlo simulation for
205 the geometry used in the irradiations, the dose rate to quartz was estimated to be 94% (with relative
206 uncertainty of 2.2%) of that to water. Details for the measurement parameters for each signal are
207 given in the supplementary material. In order to detect the existence of Ge-related paramagnetic
208 defects that are known to be less thermally stable (e.g., **Monti et al., 2021, Vyatkin and**
209 **Koshchug, 2020**), measurements were carried out at the Institute of Solid State Physics, University
210 of Latvia, immediately after irradiation. An estimated 1000 Gy dose was delivered to the sample
211 by exposing it to an X-ray lamp operated at 45 kV and 10 mA for 30 min. An X-band (9.835 GHz)
212 Bruker ELEXSYS-II E500 CW-EPR spectrometer was used for these measurements.

213 **3.4. Scanning electron microscopy and cathodoluminescence**

214 Quartz grains samples were analysed using a ZEISS GeminiSEM 360 Field Emission Scanning
215 Electron Microscope, equipped with an Integrated Pegasus EDS/EBSD system (Octane Elect Plus,
216 Velocity Plus, PV 5600-EL-PL-Vel-PL) X-ray energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) for chemical
217 analysis and a Gatan Monarc Pro spectrometer for cathodoluminescence (CL) analysis. The quartz
218 grains extracted from the samples of interest were mounted on metal stubs using double-sided
219 carbon tape and placed onto the metal stage of the microscope, inside the vacuumed specimen
220 chamber. Measurement parameters are presented in the supplementary material. Typical images
221 and EDS maps are shown in **Figure S1** and **Figure S2**, respectively.

222 3.5. Laser ablation ICP-MS

223 Several trace elements were measured in quartz grains separated from the Catalina and Retezeat
224 granites by ICP-MS (Woodhead et al., 2007). Quartz grains were washed in mild hydrochloric
225 acid and mounted in 1 inch diameter round holders in resin for each sample; 14 individual grains
226 were measured for each sample. Standards were mounted together with the unknowns in each
227 mount. Analyses were performed on a quadrupole Thermo XSeries 2 ICP-MS (Rossel et al., 2013)
228 and the sample introduction in the mass spectrometer was achieved by laser ablation using a
229 Teledyne Iridia Excimer 193 nm system. We used 35-micron diameter spot sizes in order to get a
230 strong signal. Dwell times were optimized using the HDIP software of the Iridia system. NIST
231 610, 612 and 614 were used as standards with the NIST 612 being the primary standard. ³⁰Si was
232 also measured as an internal standard.

233 4. Results

234 4.1. Optically stimulated luminescence characterisation

235 The investigated quartz extracted from granite samples yield rather dim OSL signals (Table 1) that
236 decay relatively fast with stimulation time (Figure 2 A, B). The OSL decay is similar for Catalina
237 granite, Retezat granite and Retezat sediment and reaches a constant level of approximately 20-30
238 % of the initial intensity after 5 seconds of stimulation. The OSL signal in Catalina sediment
239 sample is very bright (Table 1) and decays rapidly to a low background.

240 For Catalina granite quartz sample investigated here, Biernacka et al. (2022) separated the fast
241 OSL component by using the thermally modulated OSL stimulation (TM-OSL_{620 nm}). They have
242 shown it has a low contribution to the total OSL compared to other components. However, the
243 calculated trap parameters of the OSL signals in quartz extracted from Catalina granite are similar

244 to the ones reported for quartz OSL signals dominated by the fast component, extracted from other
245 sediments, thus showing their thermal stability and the existence of this component in signals from
246 our investigated rock samples.

247 Regarding the shape of the dose response curves, there is a similarity between the source rock and
248 derived sediments and a clear distinction between Catalina and Retezat datasets. In the Catalina
249 dataset the OSL signal reaches full saturation at 1000 Gy while in Retezat dataset it continues to
250 grow slightly (**Figure 2 C, D**).

251 **4.1.1. OSL sensitisation in nature**

252 We note that the two granite samples have similar OSL sensitivities (**Table 1**) in the range of a few
253 hundred counts in 0.308 s induced by a beta dose of 100 Gy delivered during construction of the
254 OSL dose response curve. However, the OSL signals of the sediments produced from these granites
255 are markedly different. No increase in OSL sensitivity is seen between Retezat granite and its
256 derived river sediment samples located at a maximum 5 km distance (**Table 1**). In contrast, the
257 quartz extracted from the Catalina sediment is 322 times brighter than the source rock. The distance
258 between the source rock and the sediments is similar in both catchments. Samples have been
259 collected from the river bedload. It appears that the difference in the sensitisation behaviour in
260 these two cases is in line with the contrasting results obtained by previous studies regarding the
261 effect of transport distance on OSL sensitivity (e.g. **Pietsch et al., 2008; Sawakuchi et al., 2011,**
262 **2018; Jeong and Choi, 2012; Capaldi et al., 2022; Alexanderson, 2022; Zhang et al., 2023**).
263 Such behaviour suggests that other factors besides the ones involved in natural cycling (exposure
264 to sunlight, irradiation, weathering) might play a major role in the capacity for OSL sensitisation.

265 **4.1.2. Laboratory OSL sensitisation by dosing and bleaching**

266 Laboratory sensitisation experiments are aimed at assessing the degree of OSL sensitisation in
267 quartz extracted from the bedrock sample that is caused by light exposure and irradiation which is
268 the most used explanation for OSL sensitisation in the trapped charge dating community literature
269 (e.g. **Pietsch et al., 2008; Jeong and Choi, 2012; Sawakuchi et al., 2011**). The multiple cycles
270 of transport and deposition experienced by quartz grains after it has been eroded from the bedrock
271 were reproduced in the laboratory by giving 159 cycles of 100 Gy beta dose followed by blue
272 LEDs exposure for 40 s at 125 °C and a blue LEDs bleach for 400 s at 125 °C (**Table S3**). Using
273 a stimulation light source with a spectrum similar to the natural sunlight would have mimicked
274 more closely the natural bleaching. However, the experimental setup limited us to using only the
275 blue LEDs available in the luminescence readers.

276 As seen in **Table 2**, the initial quartz OSL sensitivity of the Catalina sediment is up to 373 times
277 higher than Catalina granite. **Figure 3** shows that the laboratory sensitisation experiments sensitise
278 the OSL signal in Catalina Granite and sediments up to 3-5 times their initial value. It is also
279 observed that these multiple cycles of irradiation and light sensitises the quartz OSL signals from
280 Catalina granite to a much lower level (2 orders of magnitude less) compared to the natural
281 sensitisation reached in the sediment. This suggests that other factors, yet unknown, during
282 erosion, transport and deposition processes, play a more important role in the sensitisation process
283 than irradiation and bleaching alone.

284 However, the quartz OSL signals in the Retezat bedrock (with an initial quartz OSL sensitivity
285 similar to that of Catalina granite) as well as the derived sediment do not sensitise after repeated
286 cycles of bleaching and irradiation (**Figure 3, Table 2**). The fact that both Catalina and Retezat
287 granite have similar initial OSL sensitivity but different sensitisation behaviour, indicates that

288 characteristics of quartz in the parent rock (defects and impurities in the quartz lattice) play a major
289 role in the potential for OSL sensitisation.

290 Another noteworthy observation is that Retezat granite and sediment sensitises after heating to 500
291 °C (**Table 1**) and not after dosing and bleaching. Whereas the Catalina granite and sediments as
292 well as Tatra Mountains sediments “recently” weathered from the granitic source rock (**Moska
293 and Murray, 2006**), experience a similar increase in sensitivity after both treatments. More
294 specifically, heating to 500 °C and subsequent OSL dose response construction, produces an
295 increase in the OSL sensitivity of 6-8 times in bedrock samples and of 2-3 times in sediment
296 samples (**Table 1**).

297 **4.2. Thermally stimulated luminescence characterisation**

298 The nature of defects involved in the luminescence processes in quartz can be studied using the
299 thermoluminescence technique. It is generally assumed that the temperature of the glow peaks
300 indicates the loss of electrons from traps while the thermoluminescence spectra additionally give
301 information on recombination sites characteristics. **Figure 4 A** shows the natural quartz TL in
302 Catalina and Retezat granites. Maximum TL are recorded at 300-350 °C, however the peak is wider
303 (more contribution of high temperature, namely more than 400 °C) in Catalina granite.

304 After irradiation with 100 Gy, both samples show 110 °C TL peaks characteristic of quartz (**Figure
305 4 B**). The 110 °C TL peak in Catalina granite is wider and distorted because of intermediate
306 temperature peaks. **Figure 4 D** shows that the Retezat granite is brighter than Catalina.

307 TL emission at intermediate temperatures (150-250 °C) is recorded only in Catalina granite and
308 not in Retezat granite. As seen in **Figure 4 B** the Retezat granite shows an extremely weak emission
309 peak at 200 °C in the lower temperature region. In the higher temperature region, Retezat granite

310 shows two distinctive peaks at 280 °C and 340 °C (probably an overlap of the typical 325 °C and
311 375 °C peaks for quartz) while Catalina granite shows a broad TL peak between 280-450 °C
312 (**Figure 4 B and C**).

313 In order to gain insights into the factors that control the different sensitisation behaviour of quartz
314 OSL signals in Catalina and Retezat granites, we further investigate and compare the defect and
315 impurities in quartz by using multiple spectroscopic analyses.

316 **4.3. Electron spin resonance characterisation**

317 The paramagnetic defects in the natural quartz lattice are directly investigated by means of ESR.
318 Examples of the ESR spectra recorded for E'_1 and what we will further denote as peroxy centres
319 (an overlap of $\equiv\text{Si-O-O}\cdot$ and $\equiv\text{Si-O}\cdot$, **Timar-Gabor et al., 2023**), Al-hole ($[\text{AlO}_4]^0$), compensated
320 Ti related signals (mostly Ti-Li, $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$), are given in **Figure 5 A-H** for granites and sediments
321 samples in natural and irradiated samples. This value of 40 kGy was chosen for gamma dose
322 irradiation as we have previously shown that this dose is large enough to induce saturation of Al
323 and Ti related signals (e.g. **Benzid and Timar-Gabor 2020a, Kabacińska et al., 2022**).

324 E'_1 and peroxy are oxygen related defects (**Figure 5 A-D**). Our hypothesis is that oxygen
325 displacement is achieved by inefficient processes (such as alpha damage) that occur in the long
326 time spent by the quartz crystal in the source rock (**Dave et al., 2022a, Timar-Gabor et al., 2023**).
327 Natural E'_1 and peroxy values are higher in Retezat compared to Catalina granite which agrees
328 with the crystallization ages. These signals do not change significantly with a gamma dose of 40
329 kGy added on top of natural, in both sediments and granites (**Figure 5 B, D, Table 3**) as previously
330 reported by **Dave et al. (2022a)**.

331 In Catalina sediment the Al-hole signals (**Figure 5 E**) decrease slightly compared to bedrock due
332 to bleaching during the short transport (few km, **Table 3**). We attribute this to hole transfer from
333 Al-hole centre to the oxygen deficiency centre (ODC, $O \equiv Si - Si \equiv O$) (**Benzid and Timar-**
334 **Gabor, 2021** and references therein). During optical bleaching the hole capture at the ODC leaves
335 a single electron trapped at the oxygen vacancy leading to the formation of the E' centre in quartz.
336 Indeed, in the investigated samples from Retezat, E' ₁ values slightly increase in sediment compared
337 to the parent rock due to light exposure and then stabilises (**Table 3**). After an irradiation dose of
338 40 kGy Al-hole signals (**Figure 5 F**) are slightly higher in sediments than in the parent rock for
339 Catalina samples. This might infer that the dose saturated value of Al-hole is not a direct measure
340 of the total aluminium concentration but is probably also influenced by other impurity present that
341 change during transport and interplay with the saturation value of the above-mentioned signal.

342 Compensated Ti related defects (mostly $[TiO_4^-Li^+]^0$) are known to be more bleachable than the Al-
343 hole signals (e.g. **Kabacińska et al., 2022**), justifying the decrease of Ti-related signals in Catalina
344 sediment compared to bedrock (**Table 3**). However, the main difference in the ESR properties
345 between the two granites by far is the fact that there is no compensated Ti ESR signal visible both
346 in Retezat rock and sediment samples even after an irradiation to 40 kGy.

347 Additionally, in the irradiated peroxy ESR spectra (**Figure 5 D**), a signal beyond the 3350 G ($g =$
348 1.997) was observed, which was attributed to a Germanium-related centre. As Ge ESR signals
349 were recently reported to have a limited thermal stability (**Vyatkin and Koshchug, 2020, Monti**
350 **et al. 2021**), we have further investigated the samples immediately after irradiation (**Figure 5 I**).
351 Note that these ESR spectra are shifted towards higher magnetic fields due to a higher microwave
352 frequency. The stability of the Ge signal at room temperature was characterised by irradiating
353 (1000 Gy by X-ray lamp exposure, a dose chosen based on dose response characteristics not shown

354 here) the sample and measuring the ESR signals after different storage intervals at room
355 temperature (**Figure 5 J**, filled symbols). In the Retezat samples, the Ge-related ESR signals decay
356 after 5 hours of storage at room temperature while in Catalina samples the ESR signal is stable for
357 at least several weeks at room temperature. The effect of stimulation with light on the stability of
358 the Ge signals at room temperature was investigated by including an exposure to 450 nm laser
359 diode operated at 2 W during the storage intervals, as follows: 10 minutes storage (including 4
360 minutes of 450 nm laser stimulation), 30 minutes storage (including 15 min of 450 nm laser
361 stimulation), 60 minutes storage (including 30 min of 450 nm laser stimulation), 120 minutes
362 storage (including 60 min of 450 nm laser stimulation) and 360 min storage (including 180 min of
363 450 nm laser stimulation) (**Figure 5 J**, open symbols). In Retezat sample, stimulation with the 450
364 nm laser causes the unstable Ge-related signals to decay after 2 hours storage at room temperature
365 while a minor effect on the stable Ge signal is seen in Catalina sample due to bleaching.

366 Based on the g-factor components determined from the simulations of stable Catalina ($g_1 = 2.0006$;
367 $g_2 = 1.9974$; $g_3 = 1.9967$, **Figure 5 K**) and unstable Retezat ($g_1 = 2.0001$; $g_2 = 1.9983$; $g_3 = 1.9971$,
368 **Figure 5 L**) radiation-induced ESR signals, they are attributed to compensated Ge-Li ($[\text{GeO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$)
369 and uncompensated Ge ($[\text{GeO}_4]^-$) (**Mashkovtsev and Pan, 2013**) centres, respectively. This is also
370 in agreement with the LA-ICP-MS data (see following sections) that shows low amount of
371 germanium in both samples, but the amount of Li existent in Catalina sample is one order of
372 magnitude higher than in the Retezat sample.

373 **4.4. SEM and cathodoluminescence characterisation**

374 SEM images of individual quartz grains are displayed in **Figure S1**, while **Figure S2** presents EDS
375 maps constructed from selected pure quartz grains.

376 The total CL emission for the studied samples arises mainly from two peaks corresponding to two
377 different emission bands: a "red" 630-650 nm (1.97-1.9 eV) and a "blue" 430-450 nm (2.88-2.75
378 eV) (**Figure 6**). The CL spectra illustrate that the red peak is present in all quartz samples, while
379 the blue emission band is strong in Catalina granite and its sediment but is very weak in the Retezat
380 samples. These two bands are some of the most common CL emissions in natural quartz
381 (**Ramseyer et al. 1988; Götze et al. 2001, 2015**). Cathodoluminescence maps of the two emissions
382 are presented in **Figure S4**.

383 The 650 nm (1.9 eV) emission present in quartz samples is attributed to the so-called non-bridging
384 oxygen hole centre (NBOHC, $\equiv\text{Si}-\text{O}\cdot$) (**Skuja et al., 2020; Leeman et al., 2012; Götze et al.,**
385 **2001**). This is an intrinsic defect represented by unpaired electrons associated with oxygen atoms
386 bonded to a threefold-coordinated silicon atom. The intensity of this red emission is higher in
387 Retezat samples compared to both Catalina granite and sediment samples (**Table S4**).

388 As far as the blue emission is concerned several studies have linked this emission (450 nm, 2.7
389 eV) to the recombination of self-trapped excitons (STE) associated with oxygen vacancies in the
390 quartz structure (**Stevens-Kalceff, 2009, Götze, 2021**). However, more recent studies have
391 established a strong correlation between cathodoluminescence intensity and Ti concentration in
392 quartz, with the most intense luminescence often found in samples with elevated Ti levels
393 (**Leeman et al., 2012; Götze et al., 2024**). However, it is yet unknown what is the exact structure
394 of the Ti related defect generating this blue emission.

395 Another difference in CL between Catalina and Retezat datasets is that the 430-450 nm (2.88-2.75
396 eV) emission band is weak in Retezat samples compared to Catalina samples (**Figure 6, Table**
397 **S4**). Based on this observation, the fact that compensated Ti related ESR signals were not detected

398 in Retezat samples as well as the elemental concentrations presented in the following section, we
399 support the assignment of the 430-450 nm (2.88-2.75 eV) emission to Ti related defects.

400 4.5. LA-ICP-MS

401 A summary of Ti, Li and Ge data in ppm are shown in Table 4 for the 2 samples. Data were reduced
402 using Iolite (**Paton et al., 2011**). The rest of the data, including results for elements that proved to
403 have concentrations below the detection limit can be accessed in the open data section where we
404 also provide the raw ICP-MS data as well as the laser log file for the raw data to be viewed and
405 examined in Iolite or similar. Of all elements investigated on the two samples (CATA G and RATG
406 22-06), the most relevant differences exist between elements Ti (measured via isotope ^{49}Ti) and Li
407 (measured via isotope ^7Li). The fivefold more abundant Ti and order of magnitude more abundant
408 Li in CATA G are outstanding differences in concentrations (**Table 4**). While Table 4 averages out
409 14 grains, individual grain data show consistency among grains as reflected by the low values of
410 the relative error reported at a 95% confidence level. Since both these samples are igneous, it is
411 widely believed that Ti concentration in quartz is temperature dependent (**Wark and Watson,**
412 **2006**). The Catalina granite is an I-type granitoid with higher igneous temperatures (**Ducea et al.,**
413 **2020**) than the S-type plutons of the Retezat granitoids; consequently, the Ti concentrations in
414 measured quartz grains are easily explainable.

415 5. Discussion and proposed mechanism for OSL sensitisation in quartz

416 Many studies in optically stimulated dating community assume that optically stimulated
417 luminescence sensitivity of sediments is acquired by earth surface processes acting on the grains
418 after being weathered from the original source rock, namely the repeated exposure of the quartz
419 grains to irradiation and light exposure. But, to our knowledge, there are few studies that tackle

420 sensitisation through dosing and bleaching (exposure to light) of quartz extracted from rocks and
421 even fewer on granite rocks specifically, which is puzzling, since granites are the main quartz
422 producers in sedimentary systems. **Moska and Murray (2006)** report sensitisation of the OSL
423 signal after multiple cycles of dosing and bleaching of quartz from sediments recently detached
424 from granitic bedrock, in top of catchment in Northern Carpathians, Poland. Dose-bleach cycles
425 without any heating were carried out, reporting that the thermally stable part of the OSL signal
426 was increased by 7 times, a degree very similar to the sensitisation in Catalina granite and derived
427 sediment. Another study (**Pietsch et al., 2008**) reports comparable natural and laboratory
428 sensitisation levels of quartz OSL signals from fluvial sediments and their sandstone bedrock
429 source in Australia. Repeated cycles of irradiation and bleaching increases the OSL signal in the
430 bedrock sample 2.5 to 12 times. Downstream transport along 325 km produces a linear increase of
431 up to 5 times in luminescence sensitivity of bedload quartz. However, the observed sensitivity
432 pattern can also be influenced by changes in sediment sources due to variation in source lithologies
433 downstream. Different degrees of laboratory sensitisation are observed on fluvial samples of
434 various source lithologies along a river basin on the Tibetan Plateau by **Zhang et al. (2023)**.

435 Since the OSL signal was proposed to be composed of several components, in other words it results
436 from the excitation of several electron traps (e.g. **Jain et al., 2003**) and recently **Mineli et al.**
437 **(2021)** by performing deconvolution of linearly modulated OSL reported that the initial part of the
438 OSL decay curves from medium to high OSL sensitivity grains is dominated by the so-called fast
439 OSL component while low sensitivity OSL quartz from sediments and parent rocks is mainly
440 dominated by medium and slow components we have examined comparatively the OSL decay
441 shape of granite samples as function of irradiation dose as well as before and after the sensitisation
442 by laboratory irradiation and bleaching (**Figure S3**). We observe no significant difference between

443 the decay shapes of the two granite samples. There is no significant difference between the shape
444 of the laboratory sensitised signal and the signal recorded before the sensitisation procedure. While
445 the background of the signal is increased by a factor of 2, the signal collected in the first channel
446 of stimulation increases about 6 times. Thus, if one assumes the OSL signal as the sum of different
447 components it is reasonable to assume that the fast component is mainly sensitised by laboratory
448 bleaching and irradiation. Also, due to the sharpness of the OSL decay curve observed in quartz
449 from Catalina sediment (**Figure 2 B**) we conclude that the increase in the OSL sensitivity is
450 generally related to higher sensitisation of the fast component as previously observed for natural
451 samples by **Sawakuchi et al. (2011)**. This, however, does not necessarily imply that laboratory
452 sensitisation in nature and by bleach dose experiments in the laboratory are entirely controlled by
453 the same physical processes as discussed below.

454 In the two granite bedrock samples and their short-travelled sediments investigated here, we
455 observed contrasting OSL sensitisation behaviours. The quartz extracted from Retezat granite
456 sample does not sensitise in nature, along a (< 5 km) river catchment nor after laboratory bleaching
457 and dosing experiments. On the other hand, the quartz extracted from Catalina granite sample
458 sensitises in nature by a factor of 322 and to a much lower extent (up to 5 times) after laboratory
459 bleaching and dosing experiments. Our data indicates that: (i) other factors than bleaching and
460 irradiation exposure play a more important role in the mechanism of OSL sensitisation in nature
461 and (ii) the OSL sensitivity depends on the capacity to sensitise given by lattice defects acquired
462 by quartz during crystallisation in the source rock.

463 The main difference in TL signals between Catalina and Retezat is the lack of an emission at
464 intermediate temperature ranges (150-200 °C) in Retezat samples. **Plötze et al. (2012)** and
465 references therein suggest the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{-Li}^+]^0$ as possible electron traps for the TL peaks at 150-220

466 °C (330-340 nm), 200 °C (510 nm) and 280 °C (470-510 nm). More recently, the source of the
467 intermediate TL peaks in quartz (160 °C and 220°C) has been associated to a defect pairs involving
468 $[XO_4M^+]^0$, where X can be Ti or Ge, acting as electron traps (**Williams and Spooner, 2018** and
469 references therein). Our results, concur with the assignment of the low temperature peaks as Ti and
470 Ge related electron traps, as we were unable to identify Ti related defects or Ge-related stable
471 defects in our electron spin resonance characterisation in the Retezat sample. The g-factors
472 convincingly show unstable uncompensated Ge centres in Retezat granite and stable Ge-Li centres
473 in Catalina granite. This supports the previous statement of observing Ti-Li luminescence signals
474 in Catalina granite. A low amount of Ti in Retezat samples can be inferred by the weak "blue" 430-
475 450 nm (2.88-2.75 eV) emission observed in CL for this granite sample. Finally, this assignment
476 is strongly supported by elemental concentrations obtained by inductively coupled mass
477 spectrometry.

478 **Bøtter-Jensen et al. (1995)** proposed a mechanism of enhancement of OSL sensitivity in
479 sedimentary quartz due to high temperature annealing by alterations to the recombination centre
480 concentrations. They explain this in a simple band gap model which includes: a shallow electron
481 trap (level 1), an OSL trap (level 2), a deep electron trap (level 3), the OSL recombination radiative
482 centre, (level 4) and a non-radiative recombination centre (level 5). The effect of sensitisation
483 concerns the competing effect of concentration of luminescence centres in level 4 as compared to
484 level 5. In other words, an increase in sensitivity conceptually means either an increase in the
485 concentration of holes in level 4 compared to level 5, or a decrease of concentration of holes in
486 level 5 compared to level 4. This results in more electrons from the OSL trap recombining with
487 the radiative luminescence centres. Hence there will be more light output per unit dose, in other
488 words, higher sensitivity. While we acknowledge the existence of more complex models for

489 optically stimulated luminescence production in quartz (e.g. Bailey et al., 2001) since we have not
490 observed a major change in the shape of the OSL decay curves before are prior to laboratory
491 sensitisation, for the sake of simplicity we will consider this model, considering only one main
492 OSL trap to explain this phenomenon.

493 We show that samples that do have intermediary electron traps assigned to Ti and Ge (Li
494 compensated) impurities have the potential to sensitise. Consequently, these light sensitive
495 intermediary traps, which may trap electrons during dose bleach cycles, are likely a source of
496 electrons recombining at the non-radiative recombination centre (level 5), thus reducing
497 competition for recombination of electrons released from the main OSL trap to the main radiative
498 recombination centre (level 4). As such, the existence of Ge and mainly the more stable Ti electron
499 trap levels explains sensitisation by exposure to light and irradiation that can be achieved as these
500 traps are known from ESR experiments to be light sensitive. To illustrate the mechanism for OSL
501 sensitisation presented above, we have modified the schematic band model by **Bøtter-Jensen et**
502 **al. (1995)** to include a Ti and Ge electron trap at intermediate temperatures as indicated by the TL
503 peaks associated with them. The model is presented in **Figure 7**.

504 As far as recombination centres are concerned, all investigated samples display oxygen related
505 paramagnetic defects as well as the $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ defect centres. Also, all investigated samples show the
506 "red" CL emission at 650 nm. We assign this emission to the non-bridging oxygen hole centre
507 (NBOHC, $\equiv\text{Si}-\text{O}\cdot$) and we attribute the formation of this defect to radiation damage occurred in
508 the geological existence of the sample. In natural quartz CL spectra, **Botis et al. (2005)** and **Götze**
509 **(2009)** report that the red emission band is seen near grain boundaries and in areas exposed to
510 alpha-particle radiation. **Skuja et al. (2020)** report photoluminescence (PL) emission derived from
511 non-bridging oxygen hole centres (NBOHC) in α -quartz that can act as markers of particle

512 irradiation in quartz. As such we propose that the non-bridging oxygen hole centre has the potential
513 to be used as an indicator of the age of the source rock. On the other hand, it should not be forgotten
514 that other possible mechanism of NBOHC creation involve hydrogen- or alkali-passivated
515 precursor defects (**Stevens-Kalceff, 2009, Götze, 2021**). In natural quartz samples, hydrogen- or
516 alkali-passivated precursors on less-ordered sites, such as grain surfaces, can create oxygen
517 dangling bonds through the radiolysis of $\equiv\text{Si-O-H}$ or $\equiv\text{Si-O-}$ (alkali ion) species (**Skuja et al.,**
518 **2020**). This extrinsic mechanism, commonly observed in glassy SiO_2 , is also effective in high
519 SiOH-content microcrystalline SiO_2 , like opal or agate where intense 1.9 eV (652 nm)
520 cathodoluminescence (CL) is noted (**Götze et al., 1999**). Consequently, the destruction or creation
521 of non-bridging oxygen hole centres by this mechanism are conceivable during long time and
522 distance transport of quartz in sedimentary systems and might be influenced by their humidity.
523 **Mineli et al. (2021)** have shown empirical evidence of sensitivity increase in moist transport
524 systems. Further, studies on sensitivity of quartz from loess-palaeosol sequences shown that
525 luminescence sensitivity of quartz from loess palaeosol alternations in China Tajikistan and shows
526 systematic variations between loess and palaeosol units, with increased values in the latter (**Lü**
527 **and Sun, 2011; Lü et al., 2014, Dave et al., 2022b**). Further studies will be conducted to
528 understand if such processes play an additional role in natural OSL sensitisation.

529 **6. Conclusion**

530 We report multi-method investigations on granite samples and derived sediments, which show
531 contrasting OSL sensitisation behaviours. The laboratory sensitisation experiments indicate that
532 repeated exposure to light and irradiation produces an increase in the quartz OSL sensitivity that
533 is significantly lower compared to the natural sensitisation achieved in the sediment over a short
534 transport distance, suggesting that other factors, yet unknown, during erosion, transport and

535 deposition processes may play an important role. While the study of the various contributing
536 factors is still under progress, here our study shows that OSL sensitisation by irradiation and light
537 exposure cycles is conditioned by the potential of the crystals in the source rock to sensitise. We
538 attribute this potential to impurities in the quartz lattice such as titanium and germanium. Titanium
539 is a widely used thermometer in igneous and metamorphic rocks (e.g. **Wark and Watson, 2006**).
540 As such, a connection between luminescence properties of detrital quartz and trace elemental
541 concentrations in quartz, which are commonly traced to the specific origin of that quartz, e.g.
542 higher Ti solubilities are found in higher temperature igneous rocks, is proposed.

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Figure 1. A Geological map of Santa Catalina mountains with granite and sediment sample locations indicated. Inset shows the map location within Arizona state, USA. **B** Geological map of Retezat mountains with granite and derived sediments sampling locations. The inset shows the investigated area in Romania, southeast Europe.

Figure 2. Comparison between quartz OSL decay curves in granite samples (A) and derived sediment samples (B) after irradiation with a dose of 100 Gy and preheat to 220°C for 10 s. Data is obtained on one aliquot and is normalized to the maximum intensity. Average OSL dose response curves on granites (C) and derived sediments (D). Each data point represents an average on three aliquots. A 17 Gy test dose, a preheat to 220°C for 10 s and a cutheat to 180 °C were used. Data is fitted with a sum of two exponential functions: $I = I_0 + A_1 \times (1 - \exp(-D/D_{01})) + A_2 \times (1 - \exp(-D/D_{02}))$. Catalina granite (sample code CATA G.), Catalina sediment (CATA-SED MND), Retezat granite (RATG 22-06) and Retezat sediment (RATG 22-03). Please note that in panel B the higher background is enhanced as a visual effect due to the normalisation of the signals as the initial sensitivity in Catalina sediment is orders of magnitude higher than in Catalina granite.

Figure 3. Sensitisation of the quartz OSL signal in laboratory through 159 cycles of irradiation with 100 Gy beta dose and 470 nm (blue LEDs) bleaching at room temperature. The OSL signals are normalised to the signal recorded in the first cycle. Each data point represents an average on three aliquots. The codes of the samples analysed here are as follows: Catalina granite (CATA-G.), Catalina sediment (CATA-SED MND), Retezat granite (RATG 22-06), Retezat sediment (RATG 22-03).

Figure 4. Normalised TL glow curves induced by natural irradiation (A) and 100 Gy beta dose (B) without preheat and (C) 100 Gy beta dose with a preheat to 220 °C inserted before OSL stimulation. Heating rate is 5 °C/s. The 100 Gy TL was measured after natural TL read-out on the same aliquot. Figure 3D show the same data as in Figure 3B, but with the TL intensity expressed as counts per 1 °C. Insets in Figure 3 B and 3 D show a close-up of the TL peaks from 150 °C to 200 °C. Note that intermediate temperature peaks (150-200 °C) are visible in Catalina granite and indiscernible in Retezat granite after irradiation with 100 Gy.

Figure 5. A-I ESR spectra of the natural and irradiated E₁, peroxy, Al-hole ([AlO₄]⁰), Titanium and Germanium centres in natural quartz samples. Arrows indicate the peak-to-peak signal amplitudes.

The E₁ centre was measured at room temperature, at a modulation amplitude of 0.5 G and a microwave power of 0.02 mW. Peroxy spectra were acquired at room temperature, modulation amplitude 1 G, microwave power 2 mW. The ESR intensity of the Al-hole centre and Ti was recorded at a temperature of 90 K. The Al-hole centre was measured with a modulation amplitude of 0.1 mT and a microwave power of 2 mW. The Ti centre was

measured at a modulation amplitude of 1 G and a 10.02 mW microwave power. Ge spectra was acquired at room temperature, a microwave power of 2 mW, modulation amplitude of 1 G.

All the spectra were averaged for 3 measurements and mass normalised. Irradiated signals for sample RATG 22-03 are missing because the material was not sent for gamma irradiation. For E'_{1} , peroxy, Al-hole ($[AlO_4]^0$), Titanium centres, the samples were irradiated with 40 000 Gy at a ^{60}Co gamma source and measured within days or months after irradiation. The Germanium centre was measured immediately after being irradiated with 1000 Gy (30 min exposure to X-ray lamp 45 kV, 10 mA).

J The stability of the Ge signals at room temperature. The samples were irradiated with 1000 Gy and the ESR signals measured after different storage intervals (filled symbols). The effect of bleaching was investigated by irradiating the samples with 1000 Gy and measuring the ESR intensity after different storage intervals that included stimulation with 450 nm laser (open symbols). The dashed lines are meant as eye-guides.

K Simulation of stable Ge ESR signals induced by 1000 Gy X-ray dose and the resulted g-factor components in Catalina granite. **L** Simulation of unstable Ge ESR signals induced by 1000 Gy X-ray dose and the resulted g-factor components in Retezat granite.

Figure 6. Cathodoluminescence spectra normalised to maximum intensity illustrate the 630-650 nm (1.97-1.90 eV) peak present in all samples which is attributed to nonbridging oxygen hole centres (NBOHC). The 430-450 nm (2.88-2.75 eV) emission is very weak in the Retezat granite and sediment compared to Catalina granite and sediment. This emission has been related to titanium.

Conduction band

Valence band

Figure 7. Schematic band model proposed to explain OSL sensitisation in quartz following multiple cycles of bleaching and irradiation. It has been modified after **Bøtter-Jensen et al. (1995)** to include Ti and Ge electron traps at intermediate temperatures as indicated by the associated TL peaks.

Level 1 – shallow electron trap ($[\text{GeO}_4]^-$)

Level 1' – shallow electron trap (110 °C TL peak)

Level 2 – intermediate temperature electron trap, Ti Li compensated trap

Level 2' – intermediate temperature electron trap, Ge Li compensated trap

Level 3 – OSL trap

Level 3' – deep electron trap

Level 4 – OSL recombination centre

Level 5 – non-radiative recombination centre, deep hole trap

Levels 4 and 5 compete during recombination, and sensitisation can be achieved by a depletion of level 5 following recombination of electrons originating from the electron traps of Ti or Ge related defects.

Level 2 and 2', Ti Li and Ge Li compensated traps, are sensitive to both light and heat.

Level 3 – OSL trap refers to all OSL components (traps) sensus **Bailey (2001), Jain et al. (2003)**.

Table 1. OSL sensitivity calculated for natural test dose (17 Gy) and different regenerative doses (100 Gy, 1000 Gy) as part of the OSL dose response curves constructed prior and after heating to 500 °C. n_a indicates the number of aliquots that passed the acceptance criteria out of the total number of aliquots measured, denoted by n_t . Aliquots the post-IR OSL ratio did deviate by less than 10 % from unity and if recycling ratios deviated by less than 20 % from unity The OSL signal is integrated from the first 0.308 s of stimulation minus an early background integrated from 1.694 s to 2.310 s of stimulation.

Sample type	Sample code	n_a/n_t	OSL sensitivity (counts in 0.308 s)			OSL sensitivity after heating to 500 °C (counts in 0.308 s)		Ratio after/before heating	
			17 Gy	100 Gy	1000 Gy	100 Gy	1000 Gy	100 Gy	1000 Gy
	Catalina mountains								
Granite bedrock	CATA G.	5/5	177 ± 29	532 ± 41	4682 ± 167	3347 ± 725	15880 ± 3541	6 ± 1	3 ± 1
Fluvial sediment	CATA-SED MND	5/5	16843 ± 2507	171313 ± 5816	1429131 ± 114186	533384 ± 28376	1901737 ± 109015	3 ± 0.2	1 ± 0.1
	Retezat mountains								
Granite bedrock	RATG 22-06	3/5	400 ± 35	985 ± 76	2427 ± 338	8184 ± 556	8620 ± 742	8 ± 1	4 ± 1
Lake sediment	RATG 22-07	3/5	159 ± 55	944 ± 326	1699 ± 958	14274 ± 5348	15195 ± 5540	15 ± 8	9 ± 6
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-08	4/5	371 ± 19	1716 ± 46	4711 ± 344	31248 ± 3019	26871 ± 2054	18 ± 2	6 ± 1
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-10	5/5	323 ± 33	1149 ± 77	2110 ± 232	28051 ± 3189	23867 ± 2319	24 ± 3	11 ± 2
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-05	4/5	414 ± 49	1436 ± 27	2400 ± 152	36609 ± 3462	34299 ± 3182	25 ± 3	14 ± 2
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-03	3/5	408 ± 112	838 ± 149	1976 ± 660	2060 ± 232	3083 ± 800	2 ± 1	2 ± 1
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-02	3/5	441 ± 147	850 ± 117	1532 ± 392	5494 ± 1006	5720 ± 942	6 ± 2	4 ± 1
	Ratio sediment vs bedrock Catalina mountains		95 ± 21	322 ± 27	305 ± 27	15 ± 3	120 ± 28		
	Ratio sediment (RATG 22-03) vs bedrock Retezat mountains		1.0 ± 0.3	0.9 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.1		

Table 2. OSL sensitisation during laboratory experiment comprising 159 cycles of irradiation with 100 Gy and exposure to blue LEDs at 20 °C. The OSL signal is integrated from the first 0.308 s of stimulation minus an early background integrated from 1.694 s to 2.310 s of stimulation. n indicates the number of aliquots measured. SD represents the standard deviation and SE represents the standard error of the mean. The maximum degree of OSL sensitisation is evaluated as the ratio between the highest OSL signal and the OSL signal recorded in the first cycle (see Figure 3).

Sample	n	Average OSL sensitivity in the first cycle (counts in 0.308 s for 100 Gy)	SD	SE	Average OSL sensitivity in the 159 th cycle (counts in 0.308 s for 100 Gy)	SD	SE	Degree of OSL sensitisation after 159 cycles	SD	SE	Maximum degree of OSL sensitisation	SD	SE
CATA G.	3	1824	442	255	8534	2846	1643	4.7	1.0	0.6	4.8		0.6
CATA-SED MND	3	681763	402931	232632	1198579	574880	331907	1.9	0.5	0.3	3.4		0.7
RATG 22-06	3	1340	348	201	1382	409	236	1.0	0.1	0	1.1		0.1
RATG 22-03	3	1346	149	86	1538	156	90	1.1	0.1	0.1	1.3		0.1

Table 3. ESR results. Each sample was measured 3 times and rotated in the cavity between the measurements. E₁[·] and peroxy were measured at room temperature while Al-hole and Ti signal were measured at 90 K. The table presents mass (100 mg) normalized ESR intensities measured on coarse quartz extracts.

Type	Sample	E ₁ [·] natural	E ₁ [·] natural + 40 kGy	Peroxy natural	Peroxy natural + 40 kGy	Al-h natural	Al-h A natural + 40 kGy	Ti natural	Ti natural + 40 kGy
Granite bedrock	CATA G.	0.015±0.004	0.014±0.000	0.078±0.017	0.128±0.001	1.73±0.06	14.44±0.13	2.51±0.17	0.9±0.0
Fluvial sediment	CATA-SED MND	0.019±0.001	0.015±0.001	0.141±0.011	0.143±0.004	1.21±0.05	22.04±0.35	0.93±0.03	1.5±0.1
Granite bedrock	RATG 22-06	0.020±0.001	0.024±0.000	0.127±0.005	0.115±0.001	0.92±0.02	1.25±0.01	Below detection limit	Below detection limit
Lake sediment	RATG 22-07	0.099±0.002		0.192±0.003		0.92±0.01			
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-08	0.090±0.005		0.139±0.003		0.85±0.01			
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-10	0.052±0.002		0.150±0.005		0.93±0.02			
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-05	0.063±0.002		0.176±0.004		1.04±0.00			
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-03	0.045±0.005		0.150±0.004		1.09±0.04			
Fluvial sediment	RATG 22-02	0.038±0.001		0.137±0.006		1.16±0.04			

Table 4. Average Li, Ti and Ge concentrations and errors in quartz grains of CATA G and RATG 22-06. σ represents the standard error of the mean calculated as in Patton (2011). Trace elemental data measured by ICP-MS on samples CATA G and RATG 22-06 as well as standard materials NIST 610, 612 and 614 (concentrations in ppm and 2 sigma standard errors). NIST 612 was the primary standard used during the experiment. Every analysis is a single 35-micron spot measurement. Averages have been computed on 14 measurements.

	CATA G	error 2 σ (%)	RATG 22-06	error 2 σ (%)
Li (ppm)	8.23	4	0.46	4
Ti (ppm)	52.3	3	9.30	4
Ge (ppm)	0.6	16	0.5	12

Tracing quartz provenance: a multi-method investigation of luminescence sensitisation mechanisms of quartz from granite source rocks and derived sediments

Supplementary material

Table S 1. Sample's locations and distance from the source rock material.

Distance from bedrock sample (km)	Sample type	Sample code	Coordinates
	Granite bedrock	CATA G	32.4405 N 110.8602 W
3.5	River sediment	CATA SED MND	32.4443 N 110.8916 W
	Granite bedrock	RATG 22-06	45.3754 N 22.8729 E
< 0.1	Lake sediment	RATG 22-07	45.3754 N 22.8729 E
0.7	River sediment	RATG 22-08	45.3811 N 22.8765 E
1.7	River sediment	RATG 22-10	45.3892 N 22.8809 E
2.7	River sediment	RATG 22-05	45.3986 N 22.8817 E
3.8	River sediment	RATG 22-03	45.4075 N 22.8859 E
4.7	River sediment	RATG 22-02	45.4155 N 22.8875 E

Sample preparation

Bedrock samples were first crushed using the hammer and the Retsch BB 50 Jaw Crusher. Bulk samples of sediments and crushed rock were treated with 10 % HCl and 30 % H₂O₂ for CaCO₃ and organic matter removal. The 250-500 µm fraction was separated by wet sieving. A density separation centrifugation using heavy liquid was performed at 3000 rpm for 30 min in solutions of sodium metatungstate monohydrate (Na₆O₃₉W₁₂·H₂O) with densities of 2.62 g/cm³ and 2.75 g/cm³. The fraction with a density between 2.62 g/cm³ and 2.75 g/cm³ was etched twice for 40 minutes with 40 % HF and washed twice in 1 h bath in 10% HCl. The enriched quartz extract was resieved through the 250 µm sieve. In order to verify the purity of the quartz extracts, IR depletion

17 tests (**Duller et al, 2003**) were conducted on all the etched quartz samples. Energy dispersive
18 spectroscopy analyses confirmed that the samples are dominated by quartz.

19 **Optically stimulated luminescence measurement protocol**

20 For luminescence measurements, large multigrain aliquots were prepared by mounting the 250-
21 500 μm quartz grains in a monolayer onto 9.7 mm in diameter stainless steel disks using silicon
22 spray. Optically stimulated luminescence characterisation was performed using the Single Aliquot
23 Regenerative dose (SAR) protocol (**Murray and Wintle 2000; 2003**) as shown in **Table S2**. OSL
24 dose response curves were constructed prior and after heating to 500 °C. A test dose of 17 Gy was
25 used throughout all measurements. The net OSL signal was calculated from the first 0.308 s of the
26 OSL decay curve minus an early background assessed from the 1.538–2.307 s interval. Aliquots
27 were accepted if recycling and IR depletion ratios did not deviate by more than 30 % from unity
28 and if recuperation did not exceed 3 % of the natural sensitivity-corrected OSL signal.
29 Thermoluminescence glow curves were recorded at a heating rate of 5 °C/s. OSL sensitivity was
30 quantified as the amount of light emitted in response to a dose of 100 Gy per aliquot of quartz.
31 This dose was delivered during the construction of the laboratory dose response curve. We also
32 performed laboratory sensitisation experiments wherein three multigrain aliquots of quartz from
33 granites and derived sediment samples were subject to 159 cycles of irradiation with 100 Gy and
34 OSL bleaching at room temperature. The protocol is detailed in **Table S3**.

35 **Table S 2.** The protocol for OSL dose response curve construction and OSL sensitivity calculation.

Step	Treatment	
1	β dose = 0, 17, 34, 100, 200, 600, 1000, 0, 17, 34 Gy	
2	TL 220 °C for 10 s	
3	OSL, Blue diodes 125 °C for 40 s	
4	β dose = 17 Gy	
5	TL 180 °C for 0 s	
6	OSL, Blue diodes 125 °C for 40 s	
7	OSL, Blue diodes 280 °C for 40 s	
8	Return to Step 1 and repeat	
	TL 500 °C, 5 °C/s	
1	β dose = 0, 17, 34, 100, 200, 600, 1000, 0, 17, 34 Gy	
2	TL 220°C for 10 s	
3	OSL, Blue diodes 125 °C for 40 s	
4	β dose = 17 Gy	
5	TL 180 °C for 0 s	
6	OSL, Blue diodes 125 °C for 40 s	
7	OSL, Blue diodes 280 °C for 40 s	
8	Return to Step 1 and repeat	

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37 **Table S 3.** Protocol for the laboratory sensitisation experiment.

Step	Treatment	
1	Natural	
2	TL 220 °C for 10 s	
3	IRSL 60 °C for 100 s	
4	Blue OSL 125 °C for 40 s	
5	Blue OSL 125 °C for 400 s	
6	100 Gy β	The data obtained in the first 0.154 s of the 40 s of blue OSL stimulation was used to assess the degree of sensitisation of the OSL signal.
7	TL 220 °C 10 s	
8	IRSL 60 °C 100 s	
9	Blue OSL 125 °C 40 s	
10	Blue OSL 125 °C 400 s	
...	Repeat steps 6-10 for 159 times	

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40 **Electron spin resonance measurement parameters**

41 The E'_1 centre was measured at room temperature. E'_1 centre was recorded at a modulation
42 amplitude of 0.5 G, 3365 ± 10 G scanned magnetic field, conversion time of 75.13 ms and a
43 microwave power of 0.02 mW. The value of E'_1 intensity for each sample is an average of 3 repeat
44 measurements on the same aliquot, wherein the tube is rotated at a random angle for each
45 measurement. In addition, each repeat measurement is an average of 6 scans with a sweep time of
46 30 s each. The intensity of the E'_1 intensity was determined using the peak-to-peak height of the
47 spectrum centred at $g=2.006$ (e.g. **Dave et al, 2022**).

48 Peroxy spectra were acquired at room temperature using the following settings: 3350 ± 200 G
49 scanned magnetic field, modulation amplitude 1 G, modulation frequency 100 kHz, microwave
50 power 2 mW, conversion time 50 ms, time constant 40 ms. The signal amplitude of peroxy was
51 quantified using peak-to-peak height from $g = 2.009$ to $g = 2.003$ (**Odom and Rink, 1989**).

52 The ESR intensity of the Al-hole centre and Ti was recorded at a temperature of 90 K. The Al-hole
53 centre was measured with a modulation amplitude of 0.1 mT, 3350 ± 150 G scanned magnetic
54 field, sweep time of 120 s and a microwave power of 2 mW. The value of Al-hole centre intensity
55 is an average of 3 scans carried out by rotating the sample by 120 degrees between each scan. The
56 signal of Al-hole was quantified using peak-to-peak height from $g=2.018$ to $g=1.993$ (e.g. **Toyoda**
57 **and Falguères, 2003**).

58 For Ti measurements, the sample was scanned at a magnetic field of 3490 ± 110 G, modulation
59 amplitude of 1 G, modulation frequency of 100 kHz, a 10.02 mW microwave power, conversion
60 time of 10 ms and a time constant of 20.48 ms. Each measurement is an average obtained by
61 rotating the sample by 120 deg between each run, and each run is an average of 10 scans per

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62 measurement. Baseline correction was applied to Ti spectrum in Bruker's Xenon software using
63 polynomial function (mainly 1st or 2nd order, occasionally higher orders were necessary). Field
64 regions selected for the background correction were ~ 3410 - 3460 G and ~ 3530 - 3600 G. The
65 intensities of the Ti centre signals were measured from the top of $g = 1.979$ to the bottom of the
66 peak around $g = 1.913$ - 1.915 . For all the above-mentioned signals the ESR measurements were
67 performed within days to weeks after gamma irradiations.

68 For Ge spectra acquisition parameters were: microwave power of 2 mW, modulation amplitude of
69 1 G, 3500 ± 200 G scanned magnetic field and 4 scans. The ESR intensity was determined by
70 double integration and normalised to 100 mg for intercomparison. Simulations of ESR spectra
71 were performed using Easyspin software (Stoll and Schweiger, 2006).

72 **Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging and energy dispersive spectroscopy**

73 The morphology, topography, surface texture of individual quartz grains were analysed by means
74 of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with secondary electron (SE) detection using an Everhart-
75 Thornley detector. Secondary electrons (SE) topographical imaging was performed using an
76 accelerating voltage (EHT) of 2-4 kV and a $60 \mu\text{m}$ aperture in high current mode ($293.6 - 325.2$
77 pA beam current measured using a Faraday cup) (Figure S1). In the second stage of our analysis,
78 after identifying the grains of interest, Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) mapping is
79 employed to confirm that the material under examination is indeed quartz. EDS data for O, Si, Al,
80 Ti, Fe, Mg, and K, along with the overall spectrum, were simultaneously collected, in order to
81 identify any inclusions or other anomalies present. EDS mapping was performed using 15 kV
82 (essential to achieve sufficient X-ray counts for accurate detection), $60 \mu\text{m}$ aperture with high
83 current mode, 8.5 mm working distance, $500 \mu\text{s}$ dwell time, 16 frames and a resolution of $512 \times$
84 400 pixels, for each pixel in order to identify any inclusions or other anomalies present. EDS

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85 analysis provides a comprehensive overview of the sample's purity and the presence of possible
86 inclusions, thereby aiding in the identification of suitable grains and areas within grains for
87 subsequent Cathodoluminescence (CL) analysis (**Figure S2**).

88 **Cathodoluminescence (CL) analysis**

89 Cathodoluminescence (CL) analysis was the final stage of our investigation, wherein we focused
90 on both spectrum acquisition and panchromatic imaging, using wavelength-filtered CL imaging
91 and mapping of quartz grains. For this analysis, we employed an accelerating voltage (EHT) of 15
92 kV and a 60 μm aperture with high current mode, to ensure sufficient electron interaction and
93 generate a strong luminescence signal. A grating of 300 lines/mm was employed, providing a good
94 balance between spectral resolution and high efficiency across a broad wavelength range. The
95 maximum slit width of 3.2 mm was used to ensure sufficient counts. Based on the selected
96 parameters the spectral resolution we acquired is 0.32 nm/channel. For both CL imaging and
97 spectra, a beam exposure time of 10 s was used, in order to balance between obtaining sufficient
98 luminescence signal and minimising the potential beam damage to the sample. After each spectra
99 and image acquisition, the beam was blanked to reduce beam damage. For the panchromatic
100 images, the central wavelength was set at 550 nm, capturing the main emission bands in our quartz
101 samples. Wavelength-filtered maps were generated for the two primary emission bands observed
102 at 450 nm and 650 nm, then combined and color-coded accordingly. Spectra, panchromatic images
103 and wavelength filtered maps were generated for three zones from three different spots
104 corresponding to each sample (9 analysed spots per sample). By covering multiple different
105 regions within the grains, we ensure a relative homogenous analysis and an accurate
106 characterization of the general CL across the samples.

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Figure S 1. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of multiple quartz grains extracted from Catalina granite (A), Catalina sediment (B), Retezat granite RATG 22-06 (C) and Retezat sediment RATG 22-03 (D).

Figure S 2. The SEM-EDS overlay elemental maps of field of view (secondary electrons image), Si and Al in the investigated samples: A) Catalina granite sample, B) Catalina sediment sample, C) Retezat granite and D) Retezat sediment. The analyses confirm that the samples are dominated by quartz. The EDS maps were acquired using an accelerating voltage (EHT) of 15 kV and a 60 μm aperture with high current mode, 8.5 mm working distance, 500 μs dwell time, 16 frames and a resolution of 512 x 400 pixels.

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Figure S 3. Comparison between quartz OSL decay curves after irradiation with beta doses of 100 Gy (A) and 1000 Gy (B) and preheat to 220 °C for 10 s in Catalina and Retezat granite samples. These doses were delivered as part of the SAR protocol during OSL dose response curve construction. OSL decay curves after irradiation with 100 Gy beta dose during the 1st cycle and 159th cycle of dose bleach sensitisation on quartz extracted from Catalina granite (C) and Retezat granite (D).

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Figure S 4. SEM images of quartz grains extracted from Catalina granite (A), Catalina sediment (C), Retezat granite (E) and Retezat sediment (G). On the same region, SEM-CL maps filtered for 1.9 eV and 2.7 eV emissions, displayed in red and in blue, respectively, for Catalina granite (B), Catalina sediment (D), Retezat granite (F) and Retezat sediment (H).

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183 **Table S 4.** Descriptive statistics of the CL intensity of the “red” (630-650 nm, 1.97-1.90 eV) and
 184 “blue” (430-450, 2.88-2.75 eV). Mean – arithmetic mean of the maximum intensity values for nine
 185 measurements, taken from three different grains, with three distinct zones analysed on each grain.
 186 SD – standard deviation. SE – standard error of the mean. CL intensity was recorder in 0.31 nm
 187 channels.

Sample code	Peaks	Mean (cts/0.31 nm)	SD (cts/0.31 nm)	SE (cts/0.31 nm)
Catalina granite	blue	12408	4508	1503
	red	6932	2009	670
Catalina sediment	blue	10928	8430	2810
	red	4442	2917	972
Retezat granite	blue	4742	673	224
	red	14408	3956	1319

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